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ABSTRACT

Detailed description and analysis of the data set created and used in WP4 with 63 sites across 8 countries in Europe.

WP4. Grassland management

DELIVERABLE - WP4.1. Report on rates of soil carbon accumulation across European grasslands

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1. Background

Human-managed grasslands can sequester SOC under a range of climatic conditions and agricultural practices (Jones and Donnelly, 2004; Fornara et al., 2016). Identifying optimum grassland management combining both profitable animal production and the delivery of C sequestration is still a big challenge. In grasslands the SOC densities/stocks are sensitive to management (re-seeding, drainage conditions, grass species) and land use changes, inducing its losses or gains. Improved grazing management, inorganic and organic fertilization, species mixtures, and LUC from cropland to grassland can lead to an increased SOC, at rates ranging from 0.105 to more than 1 Mg C·ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Conant *et al.*, 2017). Soil C storage depends on C input mainly through the above and belowground parts of vegetation released to the soil and mediated by soil processes. Improved grazing management can improve conditions on many degraded soils. However, there is still high uncertainty associated with grassland ability to preserve and/or increase their SOC-stocks under different management. The challenge remains to reliably quantify annual rates of change of SOC-stocks across. Likewise, research gaps remain about how SOC-stocks might respond to changes in land-use but also to situations where grasslands remain in a permanent grassland status for many decades and could have (or not) reached a SOC-saturation point. For example, previous studies suggest that SOC-saturation may be only reached >100 years since the occurrence of a cropland-to-grassland land-use change (Poeplau et al. 2011). Recent evidence from long-term permanent grassland sites suggest that SOC accrual can continue for many decades (Fornara et al. 2016; Poulton et al. 2018). The diversification of agro-ecosystems (e.g. conversion of grasslands into silvo-pastoral systems also offers opportunities for delivering multiple ecosystem services, whereas the benefits from afforestation of grasslands across Europe remain uncertain (Poeplau et al. 2011; Bárcena et al. 2014; Fornara et al. 2018). The aim of this task is to assess how land-use and land-use change may affect SOC-stocks in grasslands across different pedoclimatic zones in Europe.

Workpackage 4 aimed to quantify changes in SOC-stocks (i.e. rates of SOC accumulation) across **grassland systems in Europe** in response to (changes in) key drivers of ecosystem functioning which include **(1) land-use (-change)** and **(2) grassland management**. To estimate the potential SOC-accumulation under management drivers, long term data with repeated soil sampling campaigns is necessary. These data can be achieved by literature review, **long-term research platforms/experiments or existing data bases (i.e. LUCAS EU soil database)**.

To estimate the potential SOC-accumulation under different management practices and pedoclimatic conditions.

WP4-T1. Land-use and land-use change

Task 4.1 sought to compile existing literature data, and in particular long-term experiments (>3 years; LTE) across European grasslands. The LTE-database as part of EJP SOIL WP7.3 (i.e. Donmez et al., 2022; Blanchy et al 2024) was consulted to complete data collection. Likewise T4.1 consulted Lucas EU soil database (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/projects/lucas>; Orgiazzi et al., 2018). Following grassland types were considered for the analyses; (1) permanent grasslands (no change in land use over decades), (2) grasslands established following a land-use change from cropland (and also the opposite from grassland to cropland), and (3) silvo-pastoral systems established from existing grassland.

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WP4-T2. Grassland management

The seeked to analyse complied on how common or new promising management practices may induce changes in SOC-stocks in grasslands across different pedoclimatic zones in Europe. The grassland management practices which can influence SOC-accumulation include:

- Inorganic (e.g. NPK) nutrient fertilization;
- Organic nutrient fertilization (mainly animal manures);
- Soil tillage and grassland reseeding;
- Grazing (and biomass removal by mowing) and its intensity;
- Irrigation;
- Enhanced silicate weathering (e.g. application of rock dust to enhance dissolution of bicarbonate ions and/or bicarbonate precipitation in soils and/or soil structure)

WP4-T3. Grassland biodiversity

The aim of this task is to assess whether increases in biodiversity (e.g., species diversity or phenotypic diversity) may be related to changes in SOC-content or SOC-stocks and quantify the magnitude of these changes. The introduction of multispecies swards in agricultural grasslands has been so far evaluated by few entrepreneur farmers and land managers and is not yet considered as common management practice. There is still uncertainty associated with the long-term benefits of greater plant species diversity under intensive management (e.g. animal grazing). The focus of this task is thus to collect evidence on how multi-species swards, which include different plant functional groups (i.e. grasses, legumes, herbs), might have on SOC-stocks.

2. Data collection : Long-term research experiments (LTE; literature review)

A total of **465 records** were collected and merged from different sources of information (i.e literature, EJP database and personal communication, see Table 2) to create a WP4 data set on **63 European locations** from **8 countries** (Tables 1). The study or experiment location of the studies are shown in Figure 1.

Table 1. The number of locations from each country which were used to form the WP4 dataset

Country	Number of locations
France	8
Germany	24
Italy	1
Netherlands	5
Spain	1
Sweden	1
Switzerland	11
United Kingdom	12

Figure 1. The locations of each experiment/ study which were used to form the WP4 dataset

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Table 2 provides the sources of information and types of studies accessed to develop the dataset. The vast majority of the data as collected from peer-reviewed publications. A small amount of data was collected from reports or where from an unpublished source. The collected data comprises (291) permanent grasslands (no change in land use over decades), (33) grasslands established following a land-use change from cropland (and also the opposite from grassland to cropland), and (93+50) silvo-pastoral systems established from existing grassland.

Table 2. The sources of information and study type used in the WP4 dataset

Source of information	Grass nutrient	LUC crop-agroforestry nutrient	LUC crop-grass	LUC grass-silvopastoral
Long-term experiment	2	0	0	0
Peer-review paper	287	50	17	83
Report	0	0	0	10
Unknown	0	0	8	0
Unpublished data	0	0	8	0

2.1. Treatment categories of the dataset

After first analyses two main **Treatment categories** could be identified in the dataset; treatment as to be compared with (control) and tested treatment with SOC change (treatment_soc_seq_measure). The number of records when mapping between these treatment categories are given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The number of data records for the two treatment variables (treatment and treatment_soc_seq_measure)

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2.1.1. Control treatment categories

There were **two control treatment categories** have been identified (i.e. control and control_ref_management), depending on the studied grassland type. As for (1) permanent grasslands (no change in land use over decades) treatment was **Nutrient management** compared to no nutrients and control, (2) grasslands established following a **land-use change from cropland** (control crop) to grassland (3) **silvo-pastoral systems** established from existing grassland with a control having not trees. The number of records when mapping between these variables are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The number of data records for the two control variables (treatment and treatment_soc_seq_measure).

2.1.2. Evaluation of studies according to a land management and land use change

Figure 4 provides an overview of the number of studies according to **land management (LMC)** and **land use change (LUC)** with data which can be classified as the control and the treatment. There were 25 studies where the control and the treatment were grassland. these were add to the category **land management (LM)**. Whereas, there were 20 studies where the control was arable, but the treatment was grassland, these studies were attributed to the category **land use change (LUC)**. Three study locations had multiple land use changes.

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Figure 4. The number of studies according to land use change according to the land use of the control and treatment

2.1.2.1. Treatment details

For grasslands without land use change, a land management treatments LMC (“**Nutrient management**”) was defined according to the main treatment factors which were applied in the data set. The most common management treatments were based on a known quantity of **inorganic or organic fertiliser**. There were very few studies with (additional) details on other management practices than fertilisation. For instance, details on the **mowing intensity or grazing were seldom provided**. Likewise, there was only one study where details on **lime applications** were given and there were no studies which had information on the **frequency of soil tillage and reseeding**. There were no studies which included irrigation treatments.

Information on the **species diversity** and the plant functional group were only given in a small of studies. Experimental evidence of how plant species diversity may influence SOC-sequestration in the long-term is thus still rare and available mainly from controlled, plot-scale experiments rather than agricultural grasslands (Fornara and Tilman 2008, Steinbeiss et al. 2008, Lange et al. 2015). More information is needed from managed grasslands across Europe, which may have been re-seeded and developed into multi-species swards.

Accordingly, these studies were all attributed to **Nutrient management** which represents 210 data records from several different studies across Europe.

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Table 3. Additional land management information communicated for individual datasets and which were attributed to the main classification Nutrient management.

Land management	# number of data records
<i>Nutrient management</i>	
inorganic or organic fertiliser	218
mowing intensity or grazing	169
lime applications	32
frequency of soil tillage and reseeded	0
species diversity	90
Irrigation	0

The **land use change treatments** (LUC) were defined according to whether the treatment and control were identical and were either pastures, moors & heathland or natural grassland. The **land use change** studies were classified according to the following groups:

Table 4. Land use change treatments (LUC)

Control treatment	Changed to	# number of data records
Crop or arable land	Grassland	47
Grassland	Agroforestry/ silvopastoral	10
Forest	Agroforestry/ silvopastoral	22

These treatments may either have a nutrient treatment or not, but the data set has not sufficient data to consider nutrient management in LUC (i.e. one at Rothamsted, UK). Likewise, the data set comprised no studies which received a biodiversity treatment. Overall, there were **53 locations** which received *nutrient management* or *land use change treatments*.

2.1.3. Evaluation of studies according to soil texture and soil type

Figure 5 provides the number of studies according to the soil texture and soil type. Soil types is actually the soil classification based on the World Reference Base (WRB) system. There were 23 study locations without any soil texture information, but just one location where the soil type was unknown. There were 32 locations where the soil type was Cambisol.

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Figure 5. The number of studies according to the soil texture and soil type.

2.1.4. Evaluation of studies according to fertilizer/ management treatment

2.1.4.1. Mineral inorganic N fertilizer

Figure 6 provides the number of studies according to the rate and type of inorganic N fertilizer applied. The most common fertilization is inorganic N fertilizer type, i.e. ammonium nitrate and this was found in 218 data record. There was a limited number of data records where the rate and type of inorganic fertiliser fertilizer was communicated.

Figure 6. The number of studies according to the rate (kg N/ ha) and type of inorganic N fertilizer treatment applied.

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2.2. Data completeness all variables

Figure 7 provides an overview of the data completeness. This is useful to provide an indication of the descriptive and the essential modelling data which were collected. For example, descriptive data includes variables such as the stone content (%), while the essential modelling data includes variables such as the clay content (%) or the soil C stocks.

Figure 7. An evaluation of the data completeness (missing vs. not missing) according to the different variables in the dataset

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2.3. Revised Data set

The data set of 465 data entries was clean and updated by removing; i.e. shallow soil depth, short management study length (<2year) and Histosol, and land use changes without grassland. The revised data set included a reduced number of data records. This cleaned data set was used for to calculate the following C stocks and for the for the following deliverables; 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

2.4. SOC stocks for LTE sites

Table 5 provides the mean SOC stock (final or end year) from the whole LTE dataset.

Table 5. A summary of the mean SOC stocks (mg_C_ha) for selected land use and management measures from long-term grassland experiments in Europe

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Emission factor	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	210	68.7	1.90	<0.0001
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	84	53.4	2.62	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	31	47.7	3.44	0.12
2 ^a	agroforestry	21	50.4	6.62	
2 ^a	grass	28	61.3	4.33	
2 ^a	wood	3	65.5	8.95	
3 ^b	Remaining grass (control)	22	69.2	3.75	0.005
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	175	66.9	2.17	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	92.1	2.94	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were management treatments tested

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Table 6 provides the mean SOC stock for seven different countries within Europe. The mean SOC stock according to the WRB soil order is given in Table 7 (WRB, 2006).

Table 6. The mean and standard error of the mean (SE) of the SOC stocks (mg_C_ha) for different European countries

Soil type	n	Mean SOC stock (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	SE SOC stock (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
France	22	37.2	4.43
Germany	63	53.2	2.21
Netherlands	10	71.7	3.6
Spain	3	95.8	7.76
Sweden	2	57.9	6.6
Switzerland	13	64.1	3.37
United Kingdom	181	70.7	2.17

Table 7. The mean and standard error of the mean (SE) of the SOC stocks (mg_C_ha) according to the soil type (WRB order)

Soil type	n	Mean SOC stock (Mg C ha ⁻¹)	SE SOC stock (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
Andosol	2	82.2	1.85
Arenosol	2	52.3	12.6
Cambisol	76	62.9	2.19
Fluvisol	12	27.1	3.27
Gleysol	6	75.4	4.64
Haplorthod	4	66.1	5.07
Luvisol	184	67.1	2.19
Regosol	3	21.6	5.92
Andosol	2	82.2	1.85
Arenosol	2	52.3	12.6

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We compare the final SOC stocks for the LTE with respect to a series of different environmental (rainfall and temperature) and physical factors (clay content) (Figures 9 through to 13).

Figure 8. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to different countries

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Figure 9. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to the WRB soil order

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Figure 10. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the annual mean temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to different countries

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Figure 11. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the annual mean temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to WRB soil orders

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Figure 12. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to different countries

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Figure 13. A comparison between the SOC stock (t C/ ha) and the mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe according to WRB soil orders

2. 5. Net SOC stocks

The net SOC stock was compared between the control and the land use treatment in Figure 14.

Figure 14. A correlation between SOC stock (Mg C ha⁻¹) for the land use treatment and control

The distribution of the net SOC stock change for different land use types is given in Figure 15. These data are the net SOC stock treatment minus the net SOC stock of the control. A wide spread in the data is shown.

Figure 15. The distribution of the net SOC stock change (Mg C ha⁻¹) according to different land use treatments

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Data set allowed to estimate the net SOC stock change for different sites, with respect to pedoclimatic site conditions, land management and land use.

2.5.1. Net SOC stock changes - Clay content

The distribution of the net SOC stock change for different clay contents given in Figure 16. These data are the net SOC stock treatment minus the net SOC stock of the control.

Figure 16. The net change per year in SOC stocks ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for different clay contents

2.5.2. Net SOC stock changes - Precipitation

The change in the net SOC stock according to the annual precipitation is given in Figure 17.

Figure 17. The net change per year in SOC stocks ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for different precipitation levels.

2.5.3. Net SOC stock changes - Study length

The change in the net SOC stock according to the different study types and management is given in Figure 18.

Figure 18. The net change per year in SOC stocks ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for different types of land use and management treatments.

2.5.4. Net SOC stock changes Land Management – Nutrient gradient

The change in the net SOC stock according to a nutrient gradient is given in Figure 19.

Figure 19. The net change per year in SOC stocks ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) for different types of land management treatments for the 0-20 and 0-30cm soil layer

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2.5.5. Net SOC stock changes Land Management “biomass use” – and Land use change

The change in the net SOC stock according to the biomass usage (mowing or grazing etc..) is given in Figure 20.

Figure 20. The net change per year in SOC stocks (Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ 0-30cm) for different types of land management treatments separating Mowing and grazing types of land use changes.

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3. Lucas Data set

3.1. Data selection

The LUCAS data was downloaded (<https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/lucas-2018-topsoil-data>) to provide a more extensive geographic representation. Grassland sites were selected using land cover code E20 (grassland without trees) and land use U111 (agriculture). This provided a larger data set covering a greater area of Europe.

Following filters were applied to select data sets for grasslands from three soil sampling campaigns (2009, 2015, 2018). The LUCAS 2009 topsoil database is available for download since September 2013. This database provides: Soil Organic carbon content, and soil physical properties. For collection the following filters were applied:

filter for grassland 3 dates

- `LUCAS_sub_gr <- LUCAS_sub[LUCAS_sub$LC1_base %in% c("E10", "E20"),]`
- `LUCAS_sub_grc <- LUCAS_sub_gr[LUCAS_sub_gr$LC1_2015 %in% c("E10", "E20"),]`
- `LUCAS_sub_grc <- LUCAS_sub_grc[LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_2018 %in% c("E10", "E20"),]`

filter for grassland without stress and same for all samplings

- `LUCAS_sub_grc_wot <- LUCAS_sub_grc[LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_base == "E20" & LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_base == LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_2015 & LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_2015 == LUCAS_sub_grc$LC1_2018,]`

filter for agricultural **land use** (majority in all countries)

- `LUCAS_sub_grc_wot <- LUCAS_sub_grc[LUCAS_sub_grc$LU1_base == "U111" & LUCAS_sub_grc$LU1_base == LUCAS_sub_grc$LU1_2015 & LUCAS_sub_grc$LU1_2015 == LUCAS_sub_grc$LU1_2018,]`
- # filter out sites without texture measurement
- `LUCAS_sub_grc_wot <- LUCAS_sub_grc_wot[LUCAS_sub_grc_wot$sand_base != 0 & LUCAS_sub_grc_wot$silt_base != 0,]`

For the LUCAS data bulk density was estimated using pedotransfer functions from Hollis et al. (2012) using equations for all other mineral horizons when SOC < 120 g kg⁻¹, and organic topsoils when SOC > 120 g kg⁻¹. Using the estimated bulk density value, we were able to calculate the soil organic carbon stocks (t C ha⁻¹).

3.2. Revise Revised Data set

The data set of 1262 data entries was clean and updated by removing selected records; i.e. missing values, outliers; in addition where the simulated plant C inputs were equal to zero. The revised data set included a reduced number of data record (#1061). This cleaned data set was used for to calculate the following C stocks and for the for the following deliverables; 4.2, 4.3, 4.4.

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3.3. Lucas Data set : SOC stocks

A summary of the mean SOC stocks in 2018 for grassland in different European countries is provided in Table 8.

Table 8. The mean and standard error of the mean and standard error (SE) of the SOC stocks (t C ha) for different European countries from grassland using the LUCAS dataset

Country	n	Mean SOC Stocks (t C ha ⁻¹)	SE SOC stock (Mg C ha ⁻¹)
Austria	44	88.6	3.64
Belgium	5	88.0	17.8
Bulgaria	28	63.0	3.44
Czech Republic	60	56.6	2.03
Denmark	2	52.5	7.23
Estonia	12	58.0	2.97
Finland	1	55.1	NA
France	306	78.6	1.48
Germany	109	83.4	2.37
Greece	8	41.4	3.09
Hungary	17	71.9	6.21
Ireland	26	95.0	4.98
Italy	38	62.5	3.55
Latvia	20	51.4	3.76
Lithuania	38	58.5	3.59
Netherlands	9	86.8	7.34
Poland	68	56.7	3.67
Portugal	8	40.0	8.14
Romania	86	61.5	2.18
Slovakia	22	60.0	4.02
Slovenia	18	90.8	7.69
Spain	57	82.3	4.79
Sweden	26	89.4	5.12
UK	53	91.7	3.34

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Lucas data sets comprised 1262 data lines though EU (Figure 21)

Figure 21. SOC stocks of grasslands in 2009 (base) and 2018 (Mg C ha⁻¹ 0-20cm) from of LUCAS data base (n=1061)

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3.3.1. Lucas Data set : SOC stocks across climatic gradient

Figure 22. SOC stocks of grasslands ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ 0-20cm$) from of LUCAS data base ($n=1022$) related to rainfall for different EU countries.

3.3.2. Lucas Data set : SOC stocks changes

SOC stock changes according to different WRB soil orders for grassland from the LUCAS data base (Figure 23)

Figure 23. SOC stocks changes of grasslands ($Mg\ C\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}\ 0-30cm$) from of LUCAS data base ($n=1061$) for different soil types across EU.

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SOC stock changes according to the clay content (%) for grassland from the LUCAS data base (Figure 24).

Figure 24. SOC stocks changes of grasslands ($\text{Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ 0-30cm) from of LUCAS data base ($n=1022$) for different clay contents and estimations of SOC change.

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